

Improving Near Real-Time Predictions of Renewable Electricity Production at Substation Level

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Abstract

With the recent urgency of the transition to a low-carbon economy, the monitoring and prediction of regional renewable energy generation over time have become increasingly important. The difficulties of renewable energy data transfer between multiple stakeholders have also caused elevated the need for more trustworthy data analytics within the energy grid. However, only a few voltage transformation facilities in the grid (i.e. substations) contain complete information about the renewable energy generated within the region. A large number of incomplete-information substations with fully-missing renewable energy data limits the analysis and policy-making related to renewable energy. This work studies the potential to transfer information from perfect-information substations to incomplete-information substations with fully-missing renewable energy data. To preserve the practicality of renewable energy prediction, a domain adaptation for zero-shot learning in sequence (DAZLS) strategy is proposed for fully-missing renewable energy prediction in substations. DAZLS is a model agnostic technique which can utilize any base model within its framework for the prediction of renewable energy generation. Using total measured power and weather information (solar irradiation and wind speed) in information-complete substations in 10 locations within the Netherlands, we developed a model to predict solar and wind power from energy producers associated with information incomplete substations via additional real-time weather data, metadata information (e.g. geospatial position, existence and capacity of renewable facilities). Using DAZLS, the average root-mean-squared error for prediction (RMSEP) is 0.07, while that of a default transfer learning model is 0.70. This meant that renewable energy sources in information-incomplete substations could be reliably monitored using weather data, meta-data and physical data, resulting in lesser investment in power meters. This approach was demonstrated for the highest frequency prediction possible in the grid, with a near-real-time frequency of 15 minutes.

Highlights

- Substations with renewable power data as predictors for substations without.
- Incorporated weather data, metadata and physical data for prediction.
- Proposed the DAZLS framework for zero-shot learning in a substation.
- Base models improve by 400 % in RMSE by applying the DAZLS approach.
- Over 90 % improvements in GHG quantification for 50 % of the substations studied.

Keywords: Renewable energy, Missing data, Zero-shot learning, Transfer learning, Energy network.

Word Count: 6012 words

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Definition
DAZLS	Domain Adaptation for Zero-Shot Learning in Sequence. The strategy proposed in this work.
GHG	Greenhouse gases.
HAL	An anonymized substation in the mid-north of the Netherlands
HFDP	An anonymized substation in the west of the Netherlands
LCA	Lifecycle assessment.
LLS	An anonymized substation in the center of the Netherlands
MCA	Misestimates in carbon avoidance.
MNZL	An anonymized substation in the mid-north of the Netherlands
NAP	Normal Amsterdam level.
NRYN	An anonymized substation in the south of the Netherlands
openSTEF	Open Short-Term Energy Forecasting package. Sometimes also referring to the default unsupervised energy splitting method within the package.
OWD	An anonymized substation in the east-north of the Netherlands
PCA	Principal component analysis.
PLS	Partial least squares.
PLS-PM	Partial least squares – Path modelling extension.
Process PLS	Process partial least squares.
RMSE	Root-mean-square error.
RMSEP	Root-mean-square error for prediction.
SDG	Sustainable development goals.
WEW	An anonymized substation in the west-north of the Netherlands
WHF	An anonymized substation in the west-north of the Netherlands
WLS	An anonymized substation in the east-south of the Netherlands
WWF	An anonymized substation in the west-north of the Netherlands
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting. A supervised machine learning model.

1. Introduction

The United Nations has provided sustainable development goals (SDGs) to be reached by 2030 [1]. SDG 7 is targeted to provide affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all. In this context, the Netherlands pledged to combat climate change by reducing at least 40% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and increasing renewable energy shares to at least 32 % compared to 1990 levels [2]. Since the year 2000, the Netherlands has promoted energy transition initiatives [3] to achieve sustainable development via micro novel configurations, patchworks of regimes, and evolving socio-technical landscapes. Kemp et al.(2007) discussed that the challenges of national governance for energy transition include ambivalence about goals, uncertainty about cause-effect relations, distributed power of control, political myopia, determination of short-term steps for long-term change and the danger of lock-in to new systems. With more investments in onshore wind energy [5] and the diffusion of photovoltaic systems among consumers [6], more renewable energy innovations are emerging [7].

The stability of the energy generation process is affected by the equilibrium of energy demand and supply. With growing renewable energy sources as supply, the requirements for predicting renewable energy generation have been increasing in interest [8]. Data analysis and data infrastructure are being developed for energy planning [9] and energy saving [10]. Machine learning algorithms have been used to predict renewable energy generation [11]. For example, multiple machine learning methods were used for wind energy forecasting [12] and solar irradiation [13]. As an example, Li et al. [14] used a multi-verse optimizer to optimize a support vector machine in predicting photovoltaic power generation. Díaz-Vico et al.[15] used a deep neural network for the predictions of solar and wind energy. Lasso, k-Nearest Neighbour, XGBoost, Support Vector Regression and Random Forest were evaluated by Demolli et al.[16] in providing accurate wind power forecasting. Despite the recent usage of machine learning [17], deep learning and statistical approaches [18] for direct renewable energy forecasting, most predictions rely on high-quality temporal information to carry out predictions.

Missing data commonly occurs in renewable energy systems and can be categorized as (i) partially missing values and (ii) fully missing data. The impact of missing data on renewable energy is critical as it deviates from the performance estimation of the system [19,20]. Further effects of missing data also create misestimates in renewable energy resources leading to bias during policy-making [21]. For example, missing data in renewable energy systems can directly affect the calculated impact in life-cycle assessment (LCA), resulting in a difference between LCA integrated certification and LCA of buildings [22].

The high-frequency quantification of carbon dioxide emission mitigation by relying on renewable energy instead of fossil fuels is crucial for international energy decision-making. However, high-frequency monitoring of solar and wind power generated is commonly missing in regional substations due to (i) costs and management of additional sensors [23], (ii) privacy challenges related to different companies operating renewable energy systems [24], and (iii) data infrastructure difficulties on large-scale [25]. Therefore, there are commonly only a few perfect-information substations and many incomplete-information substations (with fully-missing renewable fraction data) for renewable energy monitoring. In incomplete-information substations, the total load is measured while there is no information about renewable energy generated. For such cases, renewable energy quantification is challenging and rule-of-thumbs

estimation is commonly used [26]. Research on addressing partially missing values includes popular approaches of using data interpolation [27] or imputation [28] to manage missing values within a short time span. Apart from partially-missing values, problems related to fully-missing renewable energy data are often overlooked and rarely studied in the literature.

In the real grid management scenario, many substations often have fully missing data (i.e. information-incomplete substations) instead of partially-missing values, as the substation does not contain the sensors necessary for renewable energy data collection. In such cases, missing data imputation cannot be performed due to the fully missing historical renewable energy data. Related metrological analysis from Moustris et al.[29] proposed to use 7 representative locations in Greece to estimate the solar irradiation within the country. Although the work did not relate hourly-frequency solar irradiation to energy systems, it suggests that missing locations could be predicted from measurement point locations. Furthermore, Tasnim et al.[30] also recommended a cluster-based transfer learning method to be used to predict new stations from existing stations. Although the problem statements from these works are different, they suggest the potential of transfer learning and fixed representative locations for renewable energy prediction. Nevertheless, the application to provide near real-time predictions for fully-missing renewable energy generation data at the lowest substation level has never been addressed.

The use of weather information, geospatial metadata, and physical metadata to simultaneously predict the energy generation of multiple target renewable energy generation is still a research gap in the literature. This is an urgent problem because most energy monitoring substations do not record continuous data for the renewable fractions, causing fully-missing renewable energy data. In this work, we propose a framework to utilize metadata, and apply transfer learning for fully-missing data by utilizing information from fixed representative substations. With this, a high-level understanding of the underlying mechanism and performances of the regional renewable systems can be obtained to provide high-frequency reconciliation for environmental assessment or policy-making [31].

The main novelty of this work is that it is a model-agnostic framework to predict renewable energy generation in incomplete-information substations in near real-time frequency. The technique assigns information to 3 different parts (domain, adaptation, and physical information) of the model sequentially to achieve renewable energy prediction on target substations with no additional renewable energy meters required. This domain adaptation technique can be used on any data-driven model and is fully scalable to achieve renewable predictions towards sustainability. To provide a high-frequency prediction of renewable energy generation, perfect-information substations are selected and the expected performance on fully-missing data substations is validated via the leave-one-out method [32]. The combined use of weather data, geospatial and system metadata to perform zero-shot learning [33] is studied for 10 perfect-information substations in the Netherlands (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The location of the studied 10 perfect-information substations in the Netherlands. The substations have their names encoded as HAL, MNZL, OWD, WWF, WHF, WEW, LLS, HFDP, WLS and NRYN. The four subpictures represent visual examples of substations in the Netherlands with their exact location anonymized.

2. Methodology

2.1 Framework

The overall methodology of this work is illustrated in Figure 2. The main task is to transfer knowledge from complete information to incomplete-information substations for renewable energy prediction. Firstly, exploration analysis is carried out using an unsupervised learning approach by combined principal component analysis (PCA) and the Ledoit-Wolf covariance shrinkage method to uncover the underlying covariance between all the substations.

Next, a proposed domain adaption for zero-shot learning in sequence (DAZLS) strategy was deployed to exploit the domain information, metadata and physical constraints of the problem. Multiple base models and moving window sizes are tested in DAZLS, while the best model is selected and used to quantify GHG emissions and compared to an unsupervised learning approach in the OpenSTEF package [34] which was used as default in the case study. The improvement of misestimates in carbon avoidance due to using renewables (as opposed to non-renewables) are then compared for the default OpenSTEF method and the best method obtained by DAZLS.

Difficult-to-predict substations were explored using a supervised explained variance approach using Process Partial Least Squares (PLS) as a *post-hoc* analysis. The most important pathway with the most sum of explained variances and a low number of nodes in the path is selected via the Pareto no-preference method. The identified pathway provides a sequential interpretation of the explained variances for the prediction.

Figure 2: Overall methodology for data analysis and model construction

2.2 Data

For analysis, the target substation will be rotated amongst the 10 studied substations (see Figure 1) as a leave-one-out validation approach. A total of 8831 timestamps for 10 substations with 15-minutes frequency were used. Metadata is categorized into two types of metadata: (i) target metadata and (ii) source metadata (see Table 1). The input data of the model consist of weather data and the mandatorily measured total load at the substation. The purpose of the model is to provide a 15-minute interval prediction for solar and wind power generated by using information from perfect information substations to predict fully missing target substations.

Table 1: Structure of metadata, input data and output data

Variable	Rationale	Data source	Fall-backs
Target Metadata			
Maximum Capacity of Solar Power	The capacity of solar energy generation facilities is a physical aspect that is independent of weather, load and geospatial location.	This metadata can be obtained from reported or engineering design documents of solar facilities and stored as a metadata table.	This metadata can be estimated via an unsupervised learning algorithm. Directly removal still results in a functional algorithm.
Minimum Capacity of Solar Power			

Maximum Capacity of Wind Power	The capacity of wind energy generation facilities is a physical aspect that is independent of weather, load and geospatial location.	This metadata can be obtained from reported or engineering design documents of solar facilities and stored as a metadata table.	This metadata can be estimated via an unsupervised learning algorithm. Directly removal still results in a functional algorithm.
Minimum Capacity of Wind Power			
Is Solar Power present? (1 or 0)	The target location might have suitable weather for solar generation, however, no physical facility was built there.	The existence of solar generation facilities can be identified from the facilities connected to the grid in the substation region.	If this metadata is not provided, a prediction for solar power will always be made.
Is Wind power present? (1 or 0)	The target location might have suitable weather for wind generation, however, no physical facility was built there.	The existence of wind generation facilities can be identified from the facilities connected to the grid in the substation region.	If this metadata is not provided, a prediction for wind power will always be made.
Source Metadata			
Difference of Latitude in Substations	The differences in the location latitude and longitude give geospatial correlation for the model.	The latitude and longitude can be pinpointed using global positioning systems [35].	This metadata can also be obtained using other web mapping systems.
Difference of Longitude in Substation			
The Variance of Historical Input Data	The historical input data (weather and total load), and the historical variance is used as an additional feature to gauge how noisy the substation is.	This is a feature engineering technique that can be performed on the input data.	Directly removal still results in a functional algorithm.
Standard Error of Mean in Historical Input Data	The historical input data (weather and total load), and the historical standard error of mean are used as an additional feature to gauge how easily the substation deviates from the mean.	This is a feature engineering technique that can be performed on the input data.	Directly removal still results in a functional algorithm.
Input Data			
Wind speed at the location	The wind speed provides direct weather correlation to	This data can be obtained in near-real-time from the	Other weather forecasting and

	the wind power generated.	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute [36].	monitoring services can be used.
Irradiation at location	Solar irradiation provides direct weather correlation to the solar power generated.	This data can be obtained in near-real-time from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute [36].	Other weather forecasting and monitoring services can be used.
Total Load at location	The total load at the substation involves renewables and non-renewables.	This is a mandatory variable recorded in substations.	Data extrapolation is possible, however highly not recommended.
Hour-of-day	This feature is used to quantify the day-night cycle in the region.	Directly be obtained from a clock.	External clocks can be used.
Minute-of-Hour	This feature is used to quantify the short-term dynamics within the hour.	Directly be obtained from a clock.	External clocks can be used.
Output Data			
Solar Power Generated at Substation	The solar power generated is used for target fitting.	This variable is only available for information-complete substations.	Not provided for incomplete-information substations.
Wind Power Generated at Substation	The wind power generated is used for target fitting.	This variable is only available for information-complete substations.	Not provided for incomplete-information substations.

2.3 Explorative Modelling and Analysis

To explore the relationships between multi-block and multivariate input data of all substations (8831 timestamps for 10 substations), a combined principal component analysis [37] and Ledoit-Wolf covariance shrinkage estimator [38]. Firstly, for each block of input data the substation, the multivariate input data (\mathbf{X}) with number of samples (s) and number of variables (v) is dimensionally reduced using principal component analysis (PCA) to give its scores, \mathbf{T} . The general PCA equation can be provided as:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{P}^T + \mathbf{E} \quad (1)$$

This shows that the \mathbf{X} can be decomposed into \mathbf{T} and its transposed vector of the regression coefficient, \mathbf{P}^T . Here, we consider only the dimension reduction to 1 principal component per block for simple interpretation and to fit the covariance shrinkage analysis. This means that the score matrix is $\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{t}_1]$ with size $[s \times 1]$ and the regression coefficient matrix is $\mathbf{P} = [\mathbf{p}_1]$ with size $[v \times 1]$.

For blocks of data in each substation in $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{n}]$, the multi-block scores matrix \mathbf{Z} can be constructed as the following, with the size $[s \times n]$.

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t}_{1,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{t}_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{t}_{s,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{t}_{s,n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Covariance is an important property of understanding the local control of data between blocks, it also provides insight into the effects of environmental variations [39]. Covariance shrinkage methods are used to provide a covariance estimator that is more well-conditioned and accurate than directly using the sample covariance matrix [38]. The Ledoit-Wolf covariance shrinkage estimator [38] provides a robust estimation of the covariance (Σ^*) by solving the minimization problem below.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\alpha, Q, \delta, \mu} & \frac{\alpha^2 Q^2}{\delta^2} \\ \text{s. t. } \Sigma^* &= \frac{Q^2}{\delta^2} \mu \mathbf{I} + \frac{\alpha^2}{\delta^2} \mathbf{S} \\ \delta^2 &= \alpha^2 + Q^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where α , β , δ , μ are parameters to be optimized, S is the sample covariance matrix and $S = \frac{ZZ^T}{s}$. To complete the equation, I is an identity matrix of the same size as S . For interpretation, only the relative magnitude of the covariance matrix is taken into account. Hence, the absolute value of the covariance matrix, $|\Sigma^*|$ is min-max normalized between 0 to 1 and the lower triangle of the matrix is used as an adjacency matrix for an undirected graph as visualization.

2.4 Domain Adaptation for Zero-Shot Learning in Sequence (DAZLS)

Zero-shot learning for renewable prediction on unseen incomplete-information substations is challenging and can involve models with highly parameterized and nonlinear methods, which devastates the possibilities for complete interpretation. Furthermore, the variance and bias trade-off problem with zero-shot learning causes more difficulties for prediction [40]. Often in prediction, when the variations in the data are well-predicted, there is an offset in the prediction and vice-versa. This work proposes DAZLS as a generic framework that is effective even for simple machine learning methods.

The task is to predict the output data (y_t) of the target substation using data from multiple sources of other information-complete substations. In such cases, target metadata (N_s), source metadata (M_s), input data (X_s), output data (y_s) will be available for the source substation (s). The corresponding target metadata (N_t), source data (M_t), and input data (X_t) are present for the target substation, however no output data (y_t) is available (see Figure 3(a)). This problem formulates as a zero-shot learning problem [41] where the model has to carry out a prediction for the unseen target substation, using training data from other substations.

Figure 3: (a) Illustration of the zero-shot learning problem for renewable energy quantification in an incomplete-information substation. (b) Diagram illustrating domain adaptation for zero-shot learning in sequence (DAZLS) approach.

The DAZLS approach proposed here is a 3-step approach which consists of the domain model, adaptation model and physical correction model deployed in sequence (see Figure 3(b)). The DAZLS strategy is agnostic to the base model of the domain model and the adaptation model, which means any data-driven model can be plugged and played to serve this purpose. The physical correction model is specific to this task and can be easily adapted for similar applications. Firstly, the domain model (f_d) maps the input data (X_s) to the output data (y_s) in the information-complete source substations. The model gives a predicted output data (y_d) as the following.

$$y_d = f_d(X_s) \quad (4)$$

Next, the predicted output data (y_d) from the domain model is concatenated with the source metadata (M_s) and acts as input for the adaptation model (f_a) to predict the output data (y_s) again. This step maps the input-output data in the domain model into the metadata domain and provides an output prediction (y_a) as shown below.

$$y_a = f_a([y_d, M_s]) \quad (5)$$

Lastly, physically impossible predictions are removed and renormalized using the physical correction module. In this task, there is binary target metadata for which solar or wind facility is present (B). For this, the element-wise multiplication of the output prediction from the adaptation model (y_a) and the binary vector is taken as the new output (y_t). Also, the predicted power for solar or wind is min-max renormalized to fit between the maximum (C_{max}) and minimum capacity (C_{min}) of the facility, constraining the prediction to fall out of the physical capacity range.

$$y_t = y_a * B \quad (6)$$

These 3 steps complete the DAZLS strategy in using domain data, metadata and physical constraints sequentially to achieve zero-shot learning in incomplete-information substations. The base model for DAZLS that was considered in this work consists of commonly used supervised learning models including random forest regression, K-neighbors regression, multi-task lasso with internal cross-validation and partial least squares (PLS) with internal cross-validation. These base models were chosen with consideration of the balance between interpretability and nonlinear modelling capabilities. Furthermore, to account for historical dynamics in the data, a moving window is optimized within the pipeline and used to incorporate temporal information into all the base models. The window size of the moving window is automatically optimized by validation. For validation of the substations, a substation-wise leave-out-out (LOO) approach [32] is used to cycle through each possible substation as the target block for the whole DAZLS pipeline. After considering a variety of base models and moving windows, a single best model is selected based on the prediction error to be used.

2.5 Important Pathway Exploration via Process PLS

The Process Partial Least Squares (PLS) model [42] uses an inner and outer model for the supervised modelling of multi-block data. The Process PLS model is a multi-dimensional latent variable model that models explained variances (P^2) as effects between blocks in a directed acyclic graph structure. Each block of the data is modelled using a PLS model using the SIMPLS algorithm [43] and its network structure is similar to the PLS-PM (Partial Least Squares – Path Modelling Extension) model [44]. The Process PLS model has also been demonstrated to be useful for multi-block process modelling in improving conditional interpretability [45]. The details of the full algorithm can be found in [42].

In this work, Process PLS serves as a supervised learning method to explore the most important pathway that is related to the target substation of interest. We define an important pathway from Process PLS as the path which gives the most sum of explained variances ($S(p)$), which uses the least number of nodes ($N(p)$), both depending on the selected pathway. The Pareto efficient point was computed using the no-preference method [46] as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_p \|f(p) - z^{ideal}\| & (7) \\ & \text{s. t. } p \in P \\ & f(p) = \begin{bmatrix} S(p) \\ N(p) \end{bmatrix}, \quad z^{ideal} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Where p is the specific pathway, P is the collection of all the possible pathways, and the sum of explained variances (S) is computed by min-max normalizing $\sum_p P^2$ between 0 to 1. The number of nodes across the selected pathway is $N(p)$ can be obtained by counting the number of elements in the specific pathway, $count(p)$ and min-max normalizing it similarly. This Pareto efficient pathway is the most important pathway to be studied for a specific substation, as it gives contributes to the most sum of explained variances using a small number of substations (data blocks). The most important pathway provides insight into the sequential combination of substations that gives the most correlation in a parsimonious way.

2.6 Greenhouse gas emissions

The greenhouse gas (GHG) emission includes sources from solar energy, wind energy, natural gas and coal. The carbon intensity for the non-renewable average is taken from the Ecoinvent 3.5 database [47] and re-averaged using relative energy fraction from CE Delft's report to the ministry of infrastructure and water management [48].

The misestimates in carbon avoidance (MCA) due to generating renewables as opposed to non-renewables are calculated as following:

$$MCA = (y_t - y_t') \cdot (CE_{NA} - CE) \quad (8)$$

In which CE_{NA} is the carbon emission related to the non-renewable average in the Netherlands, y is the ground truth output variable (wind and solar power generation), y' is the predicted output variable, CE is the corresponding carbon emission from Table A1.

3. Results

3.1 Substation Explorative Covariance Analysis

From Figure 4(a) the network representation of the shrinkage covariance estimator is presented in an undirected graph of the substations. The covariance estimator represents the tendency for the data within the substations to vary together. The number beside the nodes of the network represents the variance of the PC1 in the substation. The corresponding network is embedded on a geospatial map to demonstrate the effects of location in covariance (see Figure 4(b)). From Figure 4(a, c), it is observed that NRYN, HAL and WWF have high variance in the substations. However, only NRYN and WWF had larger covariance with other substations. This highlights the importance of NRYN and WWF as a perfect-information substation for renewable energy reconciliation. From the geospatial location, it is expected that NRYN represents the variance due to inland weather dynamics of the country while WWF represents the combined variance at the IJsselmeer reservoir and also from the North Sea. The substation HAL captures the variance of the Northern part of the country near the North Sea, however other substations do not share such characteristics leading to lower covariances across other substations. There is also large covariance between WEW and WHF, in which they are located close to each other geospatially. In general, PCA-Ledit Wolf has shown that variables within substations have direct covariance between each other which is caused by geospatial influence, including weather effects.

Figure 4: (a) Shrinkage covariance estimator represented in an undirected graph. (b) The corresponding undirected graph on a geospatial map.

3.2 DAZLS and Models for Zero-Shot Renewable Prediction

In Figure 5(a), the standard deviation of the error (RMSEP) and mean of error are plotted to represent the variance-bias trade-off. It can be observed that the models that were using DAZLS had much better (lower) standard deviation and mean of error compared to the same models (without applying DAZLS). Models with DAZLS applied had a mean of error with a range between 0.07 to 0.18 (7-18 %) while that of the same models via default transfer learning was at around 0.71 to 0.73 (71-73 %). The standard deviation of errors is plotted in log-scale (due to models with DAZLS being too much better than the normal transfer learning model), having models using DAZLS with a standard deviation under 0.01, while that of the normal models around 0.009 to 0.025.

Figure 5: (a) Standard deviation of root mean squared error of prediction (RMSEP) against mean of RMSEP for models using DAZLS and without DAZLS (b) Applied scheme of the DAZLS framework with base models within. (c) Top 20 methods out of 80 models using DAZLS sorted by sum of errors from bottom to top. The name of the models was structured as (window size)-(domain model)-(adaptation model).

The application of DAZLS has also removed unnecessary nonlinearity from the base models by separating the task of domain modelling, adaptation modelling and physical corrections (see Figure (b)). The top 20 methods with DAZLS applied were plotted in Figure 5 (c), and the less complex model (i.e. K-Neighbours Regression) was performing better considering the sum of RMSEP. Although the nonlinear method started to show up in the 5th best method, the first 4 methods all consist of K-Neighbour Regressions with varying window sizes. The usage of DAZLS simplifies the need for nonlinearity in zero-shot learning for renewable energy prediction in substations.

The best model (1-KNeighborsRegressor-KNeighborsRegressor) from Figure 5(b) was further compared to an open-source unsupervised learning model, the energy splitting model in the OpenSTEF software package [34] for the same dataset using block-wise leave-one-out validation. From Figure 6(a) it can be observed that the best method from DAZLS significantly outperforms openSTEF method where all predictions from DAZLS were below 0.15 RMSEP. OpenSTEF had predictions around 0.2 to 0.3 RMSEP when stable, however, the prediction shoots up to very large values for stations that are not easily predicted. It is also worth mentioning that openSTEF is an unsupervised decomposition method instead of a one-shot learning method.

Figure 6: (a) Comparison of RMSEP for best method from DAZLS and openSTEF energy splitting. (b) Contour map of model error embedded onto an elevation map of the Netherlands. NAP of the Netherlands adapted from Blom-Zandstra et al. [49].

The model prediction errors for the best method of DAZLS were further studied by embedding the geographical contour map onto the elevation map of the Netherlands (see Figure 6(b)). It can be seen that the prediction error forms a peak (yellow lines) in the middle, forming a higher error area between 0.12 to 0.135. This region of the Netherlands has a negative Normal Amsterdam Level (NAP) elevation and is also highly affected by the weather from the IJsselmeer reservoir. Predictions were becoming more accurate the further the substation is away from this inaccuracy region (orange-yellow lines).

Nevertheless, we can still observe that some of the substations are still less accurately predicted than others. Looking at Figure 6(a), although the best method using DAZLS was low on average (blue bars), the substations LLS, HFDP and OWD had relatively higher prediction RMSEP than other stations. Two predictions from solar in WHF (Figure 7(a)) and wind in WWF substation (Figure 7(b)) prediction are shown to demonstrate easy-to-predict cases, while solar from OWD and wind from LLS substation were demonstrating difficult-to-predict cases.

Figure 7: Actual and DAZLS best model prediction for (a) solar energy generation in WHF substation, (b) wind energy generation in WWF substation, (c) solar energy generation in OWD substation, and (d) wind energy generation in LLS substation.

For the difficult-to-prediction substations, the main misprediction was in the prediction of the peaks in the time series, this is a generic artefact for models predicting time series in real-time. Furthermore, it can be also identified that the variances in difficult-to-predict substations were significantly larger than that of the easy-to-predict stations. Although variance correction was already included in the DAZLS framework, some prediction performance in such difficult-to-predict substations was inevitably inflated by the prediction variances.

3.3 Critical Pathway Exploration for Difficult-to-Predict Substations

For the LLS substation (see Figure 8(a)), the most important pathway comes from north to south in a sequence of HAL, MNZL, and WWF to LLS. This suggests that LLS is affected by

weather dynamics from the North Sea (from HAL), and also affected by substations that are nearby the reservoir region. In Figure 8(b), it can be observed that the renewable energy generation in the HFDP station has a pathway from HAL, MNZL, LLS, NRYN, and OWD to HFDP. This long sequence suggests that the HFDP substation has a more complex relationship with the other substations. This suggests that the HFDP substation is affected by weather dynamics from the North Sea (from HAL), and also shares similarities to inland substations which are equally distanced from the reservoir region (NRYN, OWD). Furthermore, the LLS substation was within the most important pathway of the HFDP substation, which itself is also a difficult-to-predict substation. This creates more uncertainty and variance in the HFDP substation. Next, the OWD substation (Figure 8(c)) also has a most important pathway that starts from HAL. The full pathway is HAL, HFDP, WHF, and OWD. The pathway is very similar to that of HFDP, however, WHF was selected instead of substations far down South. WHF and OWD are quite similar in latitude, which provides reasoning on why it is on the path of most explained variance.

In general, the difficult-to-predict stations have the most up north substation (HAL) as the starting node of their most important pathway, suggesting that their energy generation might be related to the weather due to the North Sea. Furthermore, two of the difficult-to-predict substations (HFDP and OWD) have each other on their most important pathway. This might suggest that there is some effect on renewable energy generation that both input data and metadata cannot capture. Nevertheless, the prediction accuracies resulting from the best model using DAZLS can outperform non-one-shot-learning (typical transfer learning) approaches and even commercial models.

Figure 8: Critical pathway and its corresponding geospatial map for (a) LLS, (b) HFDP, (c) OWD as the target substation.

3.4 Improvement in Environmental Impact Reconciliation

From utilizing the best method of DAZLS, the difference between cumulative misestimates in GHG emissions with respect to other methods using DAZLS, methods without DAZLS and unsupervised openSTEF method was compared in Figure 9(a). Overall, the method applying DAZLS significantly provided lower misestimates in GHG emissions compared to models without using DAZLS. Normal machine learning models (without DAZLS) were also performing generic transfer learning by default. Hence, they give lower misestimates in GHG emissions when compared to the openSTEF method, which was based on unsupervised decomposition. The best method applying DAZLS gave a 24 times lower cumulative MCE than the generic transfer learning method (without DAZLS) and 706,436 times lower than when compared to the unsupervised openSTEF energy splitting method.

Figure 9: (a) Average misestimates in GHG emissions of substations over time due to using openSTEF, other methods with DAZLS, best method with DAZLS and methods without DAZLS (b) Average misestimates in carbon avoidance (MCA) (renewables from non-renewables) in different substations of openSTEF and the best method applying DAZLS. (c) Percentage improvement potential (rounded to 2 decimals) in a geospatial map for the best method using DAZLS with openSTEF as a basis.

For the MCA from using renewables (as opposed to non-renewables), all the values were positive, which meant that prediction models were constantly under-estimating MCA values.

Underestimation of MCA values meant that GHG values avoidance due to renewables were not properly accounted for, seemingly giving higher GHG emissions. The best method using DAZLS had a monthly average MCA of between 0 to 130 tons CO₂-eq/month (Figure 9(b)). The openSTEF method was stable in a few substations but had large spikes up to 5×10^6 ton CO₂-eq/month. The percentage improvement in MCA by using DAZLS with the openSTEF as a basis is illustrated in Figure 9(c). There are very large improvement possibilities (close to 100%) for substations of OWD, WHF, LLS, and HFDP, despite OWD, LLS and HFDP being listed as difficult-to-predict substations. Interestingly, the substation HAL and MNZL which were highly influenced by the weather in the North Sea did not have much potential improvement in MCA. Other substations ranged between 30 % to 50 % improvement in MCA.

4 Discussion

The proposition of DAZLS allows for reliable renewable predictions in substations with fully missing renewable energy data. This allows for new possibilities for renewable energy-related applications in near real-time frequencies. The direct impact is that near real-time renewable energy quantification in any substations within the boundary is fully possible with appropriate perfect-information substations acting as boundaries [29], global weather prediction services [50], and geographical information systems [51]. The region of study is also scalable, and DAZLS can be extended to a global scale to monitor global renewable energy production. For this extended purpose, the incorporation of automatic global substation detection via satellite can be deployed to detect all the substations of interest [52].

In general, the new approach allows for various applications requiring scalable renewable data from the substation level. Improved renewable data prediction also provides additional value for reliable grid control [53]. This gives improvements in optimal demand side management, renewable energy dispatch, resolving grid conflicts, provide grid autonomy [54] for smart grid and intelligent systems. Nevertheless, the integration of such models remains an unexplored expedition and it allows for various applications related to smart cities [55], digital twins [56], energy management systems [57], etc.

For environmental impact quantification, the near real-time prediction allows precise and dynamic quantification of GHG that is avoided by using renewables as opposed to non-renewables. This opens up a bottom-up data-driven reconciliation for GHG produced by renewables. As the renewable energy predicted directly affects the energy payback time for LCA [58], substation level prediction information will be an additional consideration for system-level GHG basis in renewables quantification [59]. Furthermore, the incorporation of DAZLS can also include substation-level information in dynamic carbon accounting in regional energy markets [60]. In such cases, more accurate quantification of GHG emissions due to renewable energy can directly affect policy-making [61], energy resilience [62], and energy security [63]. This will also provide clearer targets for regional pathways toward United Nation's 2050 GHG emission goals [64].

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, we developed an effective procedure to improve any basic machine learning model for zero-shot renewable energy prediction in incomplete information substations. The proposed technique is called domain adaptation for zero-shot learning in sequence (DAZLS) in which input data and metadata are sequentially assigned to a domain model, adaptation model and physical correction model. By testing DAZLS on commonly used machine learning models, it was found that DAZLS reduces the mean of prediction error by 4 times and variance of prediction error by 3 times. DAZLS favours simple algorithms because the task of mapping the domain data and metadata has been separated into two models of different functionality. This reduces the need for highly nonlinear methods. For unsupervised substation interpretation, this works also proposed using a PCA-combined Ledoit-Wolf shrinkage covariance estimator to explore the underlying nature of the renewable energy generation within various substations. Difficult-to-predict substations can also be explored using a supervised learning approach using process PLS and studying a parsimonious pathway with the highest sum of explained variances. The implementation of the best model using DAZLS has also provided 24 times lower cumulative misestimates in GHG emissions when compared to generic transfer learning models, and 700 thousand times lower than when compared to an open-sourced unsupervised energy splitting method. The possibility of using DAZLS with any data-driven models allows for scalable improvement in carbon avoidance estimation due to using renewables as opposed to non-renewables, ensuring a more informative and resilient energy transition aimed towards sustainability.

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Supplementary Information

Table A1: Energy generation by source and its carbon intensity

Energy Source	Carbon intensity (g CO₂-eq/kWh)	Source
Natural Gas (with Combined Heat and Power)	370	Ecoinvent 3.5 [47]
Natural Gas (non- Combined Heat and Power)	640	Ecoinvent 3.5 [47]
Coal	1001	Ecoinvent 3.5 [47]
Non-Renewable Average	675.5	Ecoinvent 3.5 [47], Re-averaged using relative energy fraction from [48].
Wind	5.97	Median GHG footprint of database including 632 onshore wind parks [59]
Solar	77.2	Median GHG footprint of database including 25 Dutch PV parks between 2016-2020 [65]

Figure A1: Pareto front of pathways within Process PLS algorithm with target substation of (a) HAL, (b) HFDP, (c) LLS, (d) MNZL.

Figure A1 (Cont.): Pareto front of pathways within Process PLS algorithm with target substation of (e) NRYN, (f) OWD, (g) WEW, (h) WHF, (i) WLS, (j) WWF.

Figure A2: Misestimates in carbon emissions through time and cumulative for target station (a) HAL, (b) HFDP, (c) LLS.

Figure A2 (Cont. 1): Misestimates in carbon emissions through time and cumulative for target station (d) MNZL, (e) NRYN, (f) OWD.

Figure A2 (Cont. 2): Misestimates in carbon emissions through time and cumulative for target station (j) WWF.